

SPECIFIC PATHOMORPHOLOGY OF LIVER TISSUE IN NEONATAL SEPSIS

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Annotation: under the influence of endogenous and/or exogenous infection of babies in the perinatal period, the response reaction of immune organs that have not yet developed during fetal development develops differently (in the form of immunodeficiency) and is manifested by dystrophic and necrotic changes of most parenchymatous organs[1]. Sepsis is most common in low- and middle-income countries. About 670,000 newborns die from sepsis each year[4]. In this study, the liver tissue of infected and diagnosed sepsis babies born before and after term was studied at autopsy. It is manifested by the development of toxic dystrophy (vacuolar dystrophy) and fatty dystrophies with small droplets in hepatocytes in the systemic response of acutely developed vessels. As is known, prematurity and low body weight are considered as the main risk factors for both the development of sepsis itself in newborns and its severity [2,3,5]. Today, although a high level of progress has been achieved in the effective treatment and comparative diagnosis of this disease, nevertheless, neonatal sepsis remains a leader among the current tasks in biological and medical sciences.

Key words: neonatal period, sepsis, dystrophy, necrosis, liver, premature birth, vacuolar dystrophy.

Research object and subject: As a research object, autopsy archival materials of 29 infants who died of neonatal sepsis in 2019-2020 were selected at the Republican Pathological Anatomy Center. Histological examination of the isolated liver tissue was prepared in a standard way (stained with hemotoxylin-eosin), and its pathomorphological changes were analyzed.

Results: 19 of the 29 newborns who died from neonatal sepsis were boys (65.5%), 10 were girls (35.5%), and among them were premature babies (75, 8 percent). Early neonatal sepsis (0-7 days) - 17 cases (58.6) in the first place in mortality rates, late neonatal sepsis (8-28 days) - 12 cases in the second place (41.4%) was determined.

The studied materials:

clinically and morphologically - due to hypofunctional changes of the liver, with a sharp decrease in the rheological properties of blood, dysproteinemia, hemorrhagic syndromes and an increase in liver enzymes;

by macroscopic examination - in all cases, the color of the liver becomes dull, it has an elastic consistency, and the color of the surface and in the cut state changes to light yellow-brown, as well as the fact that the liver capsule is in a tense state;

as a result of histological examination, the microscopic analysis of staphylococcal neonatal sepsis of various etiologies revealed the following changes in the liver;

- first of all, the manifestation of microcirculatory disorders that increase with the prolongation of the duration of sepsis;
- increased development of dystrophic-necrobiotic changes in hepatocytes and sinusoidal liver cells;
- in 6 cases (20.6%) subcapsular hematomas of the liver were observed as a manifestation of hemorrhagic syndrome;
- a sharp increase in vascular permeability around the triads was manifested by diapedesis hemorrhages, active transformation of histiocytes and an increase in macrophages;
- the migration of Kupffer cells around the vein of the liver triad was detected.

Summary:

- 1) in 75.8% of cases, this pathology developed against the background of premature (premature) birth;
- 2) damage and decrease in number of endothelial cells, as well as decrease in the number of stellate macrophages (Kupffer cells);
- 3) Various degrees of expansion of sinusoidal spaces in the liver tissue in mild and moderate types of early neonatal sepsis;
- 4) Development of collicative necrosis, occurrence of multifocal foci of collicative necrosis in severe and severe types of early neonatal sepsis;
- 5) In sepsis in the late neonatal period, damage and decrease in the number of endothelial cells, as well as a decrease in the number of stellate macrophages (Kupffer cells) were found.

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